

Ferric Salt as a Substitute for Conventional Coagulant in Municipal Water Treatment

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Ferric sulphate is found to be a suitable and cheaper coagulant in Municipal Water treatment. The salt forms rapid, denser and easily settleable flocs particularly at low temperatures and thus possesses a number of additional advantages over other conventional coagulants.

A search for cheaper coagulant is gaining momentum for Municipal Water Treatment particularly in case where the source of water is surface one. A number of studies have been made with electro-phoretic study using iron and aluminium salts in the domain of Public Health Engineering¹⁻³. But a detailed study of ferric salt as a substitute for conventional coagulant in respect of utility and cost has not been made.

An attempt has been made to justify the suitability of ferric sulphate as a cheaper and more convenient coagulant for water treatment.

Experimental

River water samples (1 to 4') were collected from the Ganges at the intake point of Palta Water Works, Barrackpore. All the physico-chemical analysis of water and the studies of coagulation characteristics were performed as usual. The average quality of river water under study was given elsewhere⁴.

Commercial ferric sulphate used (as per AWWA B406-61T) was of the following specifications: (i) containing not less than 18% water soluble Fe^{+++} iron, (ii) not exceeding 3% soluble Fe^{++} iron, (iii) not exceeding 4% acidity as H_2SO_4 , (iv) not exceeding 6% insoluble matter.

Basic alum used was as per ISI [16 to 17%, Al_2O_3 , 0.5% Fe_2O_3 , no As_2O_3] specification.

Results and Discussions

A comparative study with the aforesaid coagulants (vide Table 1) revealed the fact that quantitative requirement of ferric sulphate was lower than that of basic alum. It was possibly due to the fact that the concentration of Fe^{++} per unit mass of ferric sulphate was much higher in comparison to alum. Moreover, ferric sulphate produced rapid floc. Quicker settleable flocs formation due to higher bulkiness was an additional advantage.

The analysis of settled water after application of ferric sulphate showed a marked reduction in soluble silica content and total dissolved solid (TDS) percentage. On an average, 30% of TDS was diminished because of higher sorption on iron-clay floc particles. The pH zone of coagulation with ferric sulphate was substantially lower than the corresponding pH zone of coagulation with alum.

The working pH of ferric extends from pH 4 to 12 whereas alum is only effective within 6 to 8 pH. Thus above pH 8.0, the application of alum causes residual 'alumina carry over' in the supply water whereas 'iron carry over' is very negligible owing to its low solubility as ferric hydroxide. An experimentation has shown that there is only 2 to 3% of iron retention in supply water for a raw water of turbidity 1000 p.p.m. when it is treated with 35 p.p.m. of ferric sulphate for optimal clarification. The favoured hydrolysis of ferric salt over alum is the cause for better coagulation of turbid water as shown by Miller⁵. The hydrolysed product is actually effective in reducing zeta potential of floc particles which lead to coagulation⁶.

From another experimentation, it was observed that the consumption of ferric sulphate was 2.25 times lower than ferric chloride for optimal coagulation. It was due to participation of SO_4^{--} ion in secondary phase of coagulation⁷. $Fe-(clay)_2$ positively charged myceli did undergo neutralization⁸.

With regard to working pH range the Ganges water at Palta point claims better suitability with ferric sulphate because pH level of raw water never falls below 8.0.

In 'monsoon period'⁴, relative fineness of kaolinite clay particles (mechanically disintegrated) demands higher dosage of alum. The application of ferric sulphate has been extended to the coagulation of the Ganges water during monsoon period. For example, a typical river water sample of turbidity

TABLE I—FOR OPTIMAL CLARIFICATION

Turbidity of River water	Alum reqd. in p.p.m.	Ferric sulphate reqd. (p.p.m.)	pH of alum treated water	pH of ferric sulphate treated water	Alkalinity of alum treated water (p.p.m.)	Alkalinity of ferric sulphate treated water (p.p.m.)	Salinity of alum treated water (p.p.m.)	Salinity of ferric sulphate treated water (p.p.m.)
817	36.40	25.80	7.70	7.60	80	76	12	12
984	35.70	23.20	7.60	7.50	72	65	25	25
1000	37.80	30.20	7.70	7.50	84	79	36	36
1083	42.00	33.60	7.70	7.50	88	80	12	12
1108	50.80	40.20	8.00	7.70	260	250	300†	298
1600	56.00	39.50	8.10	7.90	252	240	250†	240
1700	58.00	46.80	7.70	7.60	82	79	8	8

N.B. * Each level of turbidity is an average of 20 samples. p.p.m. means mg litre.

† Higher salinity was before Farakka Discharge [owing to dilution with Farakka discharge salinity has gone down remarkably].

1200 p.p.m. required only 45-50 p.p.m. of ferric sulphate against the alum requirement 56-80 p.p.m. The clarity of settled water in the former case was also better.

Switching over to this newer coagulant, may invite some criticism from physiological standpoint. Analysis of settled water in ferric sulphate treatment revealed residual soluble iron below 0.5 p.p.m. i.e., within permissible limit of ICMR and WHO.

From the operational point of view, it is noteworthy that active matter concentration in ferric sulphate is much higher [20% Fe_2O_3 against 16 to 17% Al_2O_3 in alum]. Storage space requirement is very small i.e., 20 cft/ton. Sample of 95% purity also discharges very small amount of sludge in coagulant vat whereas basic alum, leaves huge sludge deposit choking often the circulation pump line.

From the plant scale study it was shown that 2 to 2.5% of commercial ferric sulphate solution yields a pH within range of 3 to 3.5 that could be easily accommodated in the existing alum vat of the water works. To be overcautious against

corrosion, one acid resistant bituminous paint would be sufficient on the cement concrete walls of alum vat.

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